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Ukrainian Open Science Forum (UOSF-2024)

November 21-23, 2024 / Lviv, Ukraine

Official Programme

(Kyiv time, UTC+2h)

November 21, Thursday

10:00 – 18:00 – Plenary Session

Location 1 – Assembly Hall of the Main Building, Lviv Polytechnic National University (12 Bandera Street, Lviv, Ukraine)

Live stream on Facebook - <https://www.facebook.com/events/582435884739518/>

08:30 – 10:30		Registration of participants, discussion over coffee
10:30 – 11:00	Dr. Denys Kurbatov , Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, Prof. Yuri Bobalo , Lviv Polytechnic National University, Dr. Andrii Butenko , NAQA, Dr. Svitlana Shytikova , National Erasmus+ Office in Ukraine, Prof. Pavlo Zhezhnych , Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine	Official opening and greetings, group photo
11:00 – 11:30	Dr. Svitlana Krakovska , National Antarctic Scientific Center of Ukraine, Ukraine	Climate Action and Open Science
11:30 – 12:00	Iryna Kuchma , EIFL, Ukraine	Advancing Your Research Career with Open Science
12:00 – 12:30	Dr. Sebastian Dahle , University of Ljubljana, Slovenia / Eurodoc, Belgium	Open Science – What's Next?
12:30 – 13:00	Dr. Oleksandr Berezko , Lviv	OPTIMA, Open4UA and beyond:

	Polytechnic National University, Ukraine	Open Science and the changing academic landscape
13:00 – 14:00		Lunch Break
14:00 – 18:00	Litteris et Artibus Forum presentations from Early-Career Researchers	

14:30 – 18:00 – Hybrid Session #1

Location 2 – Zachariewicz Hall, Main Building, Lviv Polytechnic National University (12 Bandera Street, Lviv, Ukraine)

Live stream on Facebook - <https://www.facebook.com/events/1269835114066030/>

14:30 – 15:00	Dr. Lidia Borrell-Damian , Science Europe, EU (online)	
15:00 – 15:30	Dr. Tony Ross-Hellauer & Eva Kormann , TU Graz, Austria (online)	Attitudes and Behaviours Related to Academic Integrity and Open Science in Ukraine (2021-2023)
15:30 – 16:00	Dr. Pii Maria Saugmann , Eurodoc, Belgium (online)	The future(s) of research assessment
16:00 – 16:30	Dr. Brian Nosek , Center for Open Science, USA (online)	Reimagining scholarly communication in the open
16:30 – 17:00	Neil Jacobs , UKRN Open Research Programme, UK (online)	Open Research Programme at UK Reproducibility Network
17:00 – 17:30	Dr. Giulia Malaguarnera , OpenAIRE, Italy (online)	Open Science Infrastructure in support of reforming Research Assessment
17:30 – 18:00	Dr. Natalia Timus , Université Côte d'Azur, France (online)	Open Science and Open Educational Resources: Closing the Loop

November 22, Friday

09:30 – 17:00 – Session #1

Location 1 – Assembly Hall of the Main Building, Lviv Polytechnic National University (12 Bandera Street, Lviv, Ukraine)

Live stream on Facebook - <https://www.facebook.com/events/537271372457435>

09:30 – 10:00	Yurii Ivashchenko , Lviv Regional State Administration, Ukraine	Towards a Transparent Region Ecosystem Through the Development of Open Data (<i>in Ukrainian</i>)
10:00 – 11:00	Prof. Marcus Munafò , University of Bristol, UK	Going Further Together: Fostering Collaborative Approaches Through National Reproducibility Networks
11:00 – 11:15	Dr. Shorena Kurdadze , Caucasus International University, Dr. Nikoloz Vachadze , Tbilisi State Medical University, Dr. Lika Svanadze , Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University, Georgia (online)	Overview of the Georgian research culture prospects and challenges
11:15 – 11:30		Coffee Break
11:30 – 13:00	Litteris et Artibus Forum presentations from Early-Career Researchers	
13:00 – 14:00		Lunch Break
14:00 – 15:30	Ali Tahmazov (StrikePlagiarism.com), Prof. Olena Yeremenko (NAQA*), Prof. Ivan Nazarov (NAQA), Dr. Leontii Shypilov (NAQA), Prof. Pavlo Zhezhnych (Lviv Polytechnic National University), moderated by Dr. Andrii Butenko (NAQA)	Panel discussion: “Challenges in the Normative Regulation of Academic Integrity. Positive and Negative Cases of Detecting Academic Dishonesty: Methods, Principles, and Technologies” (<i>in Ukrainian</i>)
15:30 – 17:00	Dr. Yulia Ovchynnykova (Ukrainian MP), Prof. Marcus Munafò (University of Bristol), Dr. Sebastian Dahle (University of Ljubljana / Eurodoc), Iryna Kuchma (EIFL), moderated by Dr. Oleksandr Berezko (Lviv Polytechnic National University)	Panel discussion “Open Science and Advanced Research Assessment for Ukraine” by CoARA Chapter Ukraine

11:30 – 17:00 – Hybrid Session #2

Location 2 – Zachariwicz Hall, Main Building, Lviv Polytechnic National University (12 Bandera Street, Lviv, Ukraine)

Live stream on Facebook - <https://www.facebook.com/events/1245596296692078/>

11:30 – 13:00	Prof. Marcus Munafò, Dr. Oleksandr Berezko, Prof. Pavlo Zhezhnych, UARN members	Establishment of the Ukrainian Reproducibility Network (UARN)**
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13:00 – 14:30		Lunch Break
14:30 – 15:00	Prof. Fabien Borget , Aix-Marseille University, France (online)	News from CoARA Chapter France
15:00 – 15:30	Prof. Stanisław Kistryn , Jagiellonian University, Poland (online)	News from CoARA Chapter Poland
15:30 – 15:45	Sofiia Bezuhla & Glib Sokolov , U AID Stichting, Netherlands (online)	Resilience and Renewal: Navigating the Future of Ukrainian Higher Education Amid Conflict
15:45 – 16:00	Laura Henderson , Frontiers, Switzerland (online)	Open Minds, Early Start: Cultivating the Future of Open Science
16:00 – 16:30	Stefania Oikonomou, Dr. Katerina Zourou, & Dr. Kateryna Boichenko , Web2Learn, Greece (online)	Forging academic and societal resilience through open innovation
16:30 – 17:00	Anna Shylina & Tetiana Kovalska , NAQA, Ukraine (online)	NAQA's constellation of Erasmus+ projects: ensuring collaboration and synergy (SEQA-ESG2, SimS, SMART-PL, DigiUni, DOMANI, CLOUD-HED, UkraineDigiTrans)

18:00 – Informal discussion starts (location TBA, invitation-only).

November 23, Saturday

10:30 – 13:00 – Hybrid Session #3

Location 3 – Room 101, Academic Building #9, Lviv Polytechnic National University (Svyatoho Yura Square, 9)

Live stream on Facebook - <https://www.facebook.com/events/1296684631511334>

10:30 – 11:00	Eric Piaget , EUTOPIA Alliance, Belgium (online)	Science Diplomacy and Open Science in a Turbulent World
11:00 – 11:30	Gareth O'Neill , Technopolis Group, Netherlands (online)	Revitalising Research(er) Assessment
11:30 – 12:00	Dr. Olga Polotska , National Research Foundation of Ukraine, Ukraine (online)	Advancing CoARA principles in the assessment of R&D projects submitted to NRFU calls for proposals

12:00 – 12:30	Dr. Oleksandr Ivashchuk & Dr. Oleksandr Berezko , Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine	Green and digital transitions as a background of sustainable research ecosystem development in Ukraine
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11:30 – 13:00 – Workshop by StrikePlagiarism.com and NAQA

Location 4 – Assembly Hall of the Scientific and Technical Library, Lviv Polytechnic National University (1 Profesorska Street, Lviv, Ukraine)

11:30 – 13:00	StrikePlagiarism.com and NAQA teams	Workshop on academic integrity: tools for detection
13:00 – 13:30		Wrapping up and conclusions.

* NAQA – National Agency for Higher Education Quality Assurance, Ukraine

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